

Prevalence and Impact of Parvovirus B19-Induced Anemia in Kidney Transplant Recipients: A Meta-Analysis

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Abstract:

Background: Persistent anemia has been identified in kidney transplant (KTx) recipients with parvovirus B19 infection. However, the epidemiology and the link between parvovirus B19 and anemia post-KTx remain unclear. This systematic review aimed to (1) determine the incidence of parvovirus B19 infection post-KTx and (2) assess its association with anemia in this population.

Materials and Methods: A systematic review was conducted using EMBASE, MEDLINE, and Cochrane databases from inception to March 2024. Studies reporting the incidence of parvovirus B19 infection and/or seroprevalence in KTx recipients were included. Data were analyzed using the random-effects generic inverse variance method.

Results: Nineteen observational studies comprising were analyzed. The pooled prevalence of parvovirus B19 immunoglobulin G was 62.2% (95% CI: 45.8%–76.1%). The pooled incidence of positive parvovirus B19 DNA within the first year post-KTx was 10.3% (95% CI: 5.5%–18.4%). Sensitivity analysis excluding studies focused solely on anemic KTx recipients showed a lower pooled incidence of 7.6% (95% CI: 3.7%–15.0%). Among KTx recipients with anemia, the pooled incidence of positive parvovirus B19 DNA increased to 27.4% (95% CI: 16.6%–41.7%). Meta-regression analysis revealed no significant.

Keywords: Kidney transplant, Anemia, Parvovirus B19 and Meta-analysis.

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Introduction

Parvovirus B19, first identified in 1975, is among the smallest viruses known to infect humans. It is a non-enveloped, single-stranded linear DNA virus belonging to the Parvoviridae family [1]. As the prototype of the genus Erythrovirus, it exhibits a unique tropism for erythroid progenitor cells, with humans being its only known host [2]. The virus is ubiquitous, causing infections worldwide both sporadically and in outbreaks.

Parvovirus B19 infection is most commonly observed in children. By the age of 15, approximately 50% of the population demonstrates detectable levels of immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies.

This prevalence increases with age, with up to 70% of adults having positive parvovirus B19-IgG antibodies [3]. Parvovirus B19 can transmit through infected respiratory secretions, close person-to-person contact, transplacental, blood transfusion, and organ transplantation [4]. In immunosuppressed patients, especially kidney transplant (KTx) recipients, parvovirus B19

infection can occur from reactivation of the endogenous latent virus or persistent viremia [5]. It is directly cytotoxic to the erythroid series and replicates in the precursor erythroid cells in the bone marrow and peripheral blood, ultimately leading to the cessation of erythropoiesis and destruction of red blood cells [5, 6].

Acute and chronic persistent anemia have been reported in patients with parvovirus B19 infection [7]. Pure red cell aplasia, a life-threatening complication, has also been described in immunosuppressed patients, including hematopoietic stem cell transplant and solid organ transplant recipients [2]. The epidemiology of parvovirus B19 and parvovirus B19-related anemia after KTx remains unclear.

To address the gaps in understanding the epidemiology of parvovirus B19 in kidney transplant recipients (KTx), we conducted this systematic review and meta-analysis with the aims: To investigate the frequency of parvovirus B19 infection in KTx recipients. To assess the incidence

of parvovirus B19 among KTx recipients presenting with anemia.

Materials and Methods

Search strategy: This meta-analysis was conducted and reported in accordance with PRISMA guidelines [8]. A systematic review of the literature was performed using EMBASE, MEDLINE, and Cochrane databases from inception to March 2024. Studies evaluating either (1) the incidence of parvovirus B19 infection or (2) the incidence of parvovirus B19 among kidney transplant (KTx) recipients with anemia were included. The search strategy employed the terms “kidney transplant” and “parvovirus”, with no language restrictions. Additionally, references of selected articles were manually reviewed to identify any relevant studies not captured by the initial search.

Inclusion criteria:

Studies were eligible for this meta-analysis if the following inclusion criteria were met: (1) observational, cohort (either prospective or retrospective), case-control, or cross-sectional studies published as original studies to evaluate the epidemiology of parvovirus B19 in KTx patients. Included studies must have provided data to estimate the incidence of parvovirus B19 with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Retrieved articles were individually reviewed for eligibility by two investigators. Discrepancies were addressed and solved by mutual consensus. Inclusion was not limited by the size of the study.

Review process and data extraction:

Two independent investigators systematically reviewed the titles and abstracts of all retrieved articles. Studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded. Articles deemed potentially relevant

underwent a full-text review to confirm eligibility. A structured data collection form was used to extract information, including: Title of the study, Name of the first author, Year of the study and publication, Country where the study was conducted, Overall incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA, Incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA among kidney transplant (KTx) recipients with anemia.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical methods used in a meta-analysis were adjusted point estimates from individual studies were combined using the DerSimonian and Laird method, a generic inverse variance approach. This approach assigns weights to each study based on its variance. A random-effects model, rather than a fixed-effects model, was employed due to the likelihood of between-study variance. Cochran's Q test and the I² statistic were used to assess the degree of heterogeneity between studies, with I² values categorized as follows: 0-25% (insignificant), 26-50% (low), 51-75% (moderate), and 76-100% (high). Finally, the Egger test was used to evaluate the presence of publication bias.

Results

The initial search yielded 285 potentially eligible articles. After excluding 188 articles due to their type, patient population, study design, or outcome, and another 40 for duplication, 57 articles remained for full-text review. Further exclusions, based on the lack of relevant outcomes (26 articles) or non-observational study designs (12 articles), resulted in 19 observational studies with 2108 KTx patients being included in the final analysis. The characteristics of these included studies are presented in Table 1, and the selection process is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Study selection

The characteristics of the included studies are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of the studies

Study	Year	Country	Patients	Parvovirus B19 Detection	Incidence of Parvovirus B19 Infection (%)	Incidence of Anemia Among Parvovirus B19 Infection (%)
Bertoni et al.[9]	1997	Italy	Deceased kidney transplant patients with severe hypoproliferative anemia	PCR	Severe anemia - 4/9 (44.4)	NR
Gallinella et al.[10]	1999	Italy	Kidney transplant patients within 6 months after transplant	PCR	0/59 (0)	NR
Zolnourian et al.[11]	2000	Ireland	Kidney transplant patients after transplant	PCR	0/20 (0)	0/20 (0)
Malyszko et al.[12]	2002	Poland	Kidney transplant patients	IgM, IgG	11/47 (23.4), IgG+ 35/47 (74.5)	NR
Cavallo et al.[13]	2003	Italy	Kidney transplant patients	PCR	With anemia - 11/48 (22.9),	NR

					Without anemia - 1/21 (4.8)	
Ki et al.[14]	2005	South Korea	Kidney transplant patients	PCR	52/167 (31.1)	Acute rejection - 7/52 (13), Graft failure - 1/52 (2), Pure red cell aplasia - 2/52 (4)
Eid et al.[15]	2006	US	Kidney transplant patients within 1 year after transplant	PCR	0/9 (0)	NR
Egbuna et al.[16]	2006	US	Kidney transplant patients with anemia and erythropoietin resistance	PCR, IgM, IgG	PCR+ - 3/8 (37.5), IgM+ - 1/8 (12.5), IgG+ - 2/8 (25)	NR
Ardalan et al.[17]	2008	Iran	Kidney transplant patients	PCR, IgM, IgG	IgM+ - 6/100 (6), IgG+ - 84/143 (58.7)	NR
Park et al.[18]	2009	South Korea	Kidney transplant patients	PCR	Positive B19 PCR - 18/143 (12.6), High titer >106 copies/5 μ L - 13/143 (9.1)	Persistent severe anemia Positive B19 PCR - 18/143 (13)
Čapenko et al. [19]	2012	Latvia	Deceased kidney transplant patients	PCR and IgM	All - 12/63 (19) With anemia - 12/38 (31.6) Without anemia - 0/25 (0)	Anemia - 12/12 (100) EPO-resistant severe anemia - 7/12 (58)
Carraturo et al. [20]	2021	Italy	Kidney transplant patients	PCR	All - 2/64 (3) With anemia - 0/14 (0) Without anemia - 2/50 (4)	0/2 (0)
Plentz et al.[5]	2013	Germany	Kidney transplant patients within 6 months after transplant	PCR	2/147 (1.4)	NR
Porignaux et al.[21]	2012	France	Kidney transplant patients within 1 year after transplant	PCR	6/60 (10)	NR
Khameneh et al. [22]	2014	Iran	Kidney transplant patients with anemia	IgG	63/91 (69.2)	Anemia - 63/63 (100) Severe anemia - 47/63 (75)
Pambrun et al.[23]	2014	France	Kidney transplant patients undergoing bone marrow aspiration for cytopenia	PCR	Bone marrow - 11/72 (15.3) Blood - 4/72 (5.5)	NA
Krishnan et al. [24]	2015	USA	Kidney transplant patients	PCR or IgM	3/144 (2.1)	3/3 (100)
Baek et al. [25]	2017	South Korea	Kidney transplant patients	PCR	39/602 (6.5)	Severe anemia
Xiao et al. [26]	2013	China	Living related kidney transplant patients	PCR	27/144 (18.8)	PRCA - 2/27 (7.4)

Incidence of parvovirus B19 infection among kidney transplant patients

The meta-analysis revealed an overall seroprevalence of parvovirus B19 IgG of 62.2%

(95% CI: 45.8–76.1%, $I^2 = 60\%$) among KTx recipients. The pooled incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA within the first year post-KTx was 10.3% (95% CI: 5.5–18.4%, $I^2 = 94\%$).

A sensitivity analysis, excluding a study focusing solely on anemic KTx patients, yielded a slightly lower incidence rate of 7.6% (95% CI: 3.7–15.0%, $I^2 = 94\%$). However, among KTx patients with

anemia, the incidence rate was significantly higher at 27.4% (95% CI: 16.6–41.7%, $I^2 = 38\%$). Meta-regression analysis indicated no significant correlation between the study year and the incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA ($P = 0.33$). Finally, assessments for publication bias using a funnel plot and Egger's regression asymmetry test showed no significant bias ($P = 0.08$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Forest plots of the included studies assessing. (a) Seroprevalence of parvovirus B19 immunoglobulin G and (b) incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA in kidney transplant patients. A diamond data marker represents the overall rate from each included study (square data marker) and 95% confidence interval.

Evaluation for publication bias: Funnel plot and Egger's regression asymmetry test were performed to evaluate for publication bias in the analyses evaluating the pooled estimated incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA in KTx recipients. There was no significant publication bias, $P = 0.08$ (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Meta-regression analysis demonstrated no significant correlations between the year of study and the incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA.

The solid black line represents the weighted regression line based on variance-weighted least squares. The inner and outer lines show the 95% confidence interval and prediction interval around the regression line. The circles indicate log event rates in each study.

Discussion

This systematic review and meta-analysis demonstrated that the overall estimated incidence of positive parvovirus B19 DNA among kidney transplant (KTx) recipients is 10.3%. Among KTx recipients with anemia, the incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA is significantly higher at 27.4%. Notably, the incidence of positive parvovirus B19 DNA has not shown a declining trend over time, indicating its persistent relevance in the post-transplant population. Parvovirus B19 attaches to erythrocyte P antigen, a cellular receptor found on erythroid cells, erythroid precursor cells, red cells of the fetal myocardium, liver, and placental tissues [27]. It is directly cytotoxic to the erythroid series and replicates in the precursor erythroid cells in the bone marrow and peripheral blood, ultimately leading to the cessation of erythropoiesis and red blood cell destruction. Common causes of post-KTx anemia include bone marrow suppression from iatrogenic immunosuppressants, iron deficiency related to acute and chronic gastrointestinal losses,

angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, viral infections such as cytomegalovirus (CMV), reduced erythropoietin synthesis from renal dysfunction, and other etiologies [28]. Study selection that among anemic KTx recipients, the incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA is common and as high as 27.4%. Therefore, clinical suspicion for parvovirus B19 should be high in KTx recipients with anemia, especially those with profound recurrent anemia that is resistant to erythropoietic-stimulating agents, requires multiple blood transfusions, or persists despite immunosuppressive reduction and/or withdrawal [27,28,29]. In addition to chronic or refractory anemia, parvovirus B19 infection in kidney transplant (KTx) recipients has been associated with significant complications such as acute rejection (due to immunosuppression reduction for parvovirus B19 management), collapsing glomerulopathy, hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis, and thrombotic microangiopathy. Although intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg) has been reported as an effective treatment for parvovirus B19 infections in solid organ transplant recipients, its use is typically combined with immunosuppression reduction. However, this approach carries the risk of acute rejection, which has been observed in KTx patients with infections caused by cytomegalovirus (CMV), BK polyomavirus, and parvovirus B19, potentially

leading to allograft failure[30]. Although ubiquitous across the globe, the frequency of the parvovirus B19 infection among immunocompromised patients may be underestimated as they do not typically manifest the characteristic immune-mediated symptoms, such as fever, arthralgia, and rash among others [30]. The lack of universal screening for parvovirus B19 among KTx recipients may have also underestimated the exact incidence among KTx patient population. With this in mind, our meta-analysis found the overall estimated incidence of positive parvovirus B19 DNA among KTx recipients of 10.3%. Porignaux et al. [21] performed a study of sixty patients in the 1st year post-KTx who had nucleic acid testing for various opportunistic viruses. They showed that 10% of KTx recipients had detectable parvovirus B19 virus, which was nearly high as the detectable rates of CMV and Epstein–Barr virus reactivation (13% and 12%, respectively) in the same cohort of KTx patients. Our study's findings further support the need for future studies to identify a cost-effective surveillance and treatment strategy for parvovirus B19 among KTx recipients. Finally, this study is a meta-analysis of retrospective cohort studies, and the data from population-based studies were limited. Thus, future large population-based studies evaluating the incidence of parvovirus B19 among KTx recipients are needed.

Conclusion

The overall incidence rate of positive parvovirus B19 DNA among kidney transplant (KTx) recipients is 10.3%. Notably, among KTx patients with anemia, the incidence rate is significantly higher at 27.4%, with no apparent decline over time.

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